

Security Constraints for Placement of Latency Sensitive 5G MEC Applications

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Abstract—Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) is one of the key enablers in 5G, offering to external parties computing capabilities very close to the end users. To attain this objective, the 5G operator needs to provide distributed computing infrastructure tightly integrated with its network. In this paper, we propose a model for MEC infrastructure and MEC applications together with the definition of the problem of optimal application placement taking into account various constraints including security imposed by technical and business conditions. Data models for virtualized MEC infrastructure based on virtual machines and MEC standardization are proposed. Furthermore, the implementation of the proposed data models for MEC applications orchestration on the OpenStack platform is presented.

Index Terms—5G, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC), MEC application placement, MEC Orchestrator

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) in 5G will allow mobile network operators to become a crucial player in the computing continuum (Cloud-Edge-IoT). However, currently, there is no widely adopted MEC architecture. Moreover, non-standardized hybrid solutions are proposed by many solution providers, including hyperscalers. Due to the diversity of possible edge computing deployment models, the design of an edge infrastructure for a mobile network operator is a complex process that should take into account many factors stemming from available physical resources (locations, transport networks), ongoing 5G deployment process and future evolution of network infrastructure, offered services and hosted applications. The main advantage of MEC is the location of computing resources close to end devices, that minimizes both the latency of communication between devices and relevant applications and consumed core network bandwidth. Hence, some new solutions are enabled, that are not feasible with current cloud computing services. Vertical industries, also known as verticals, explore these opportunities

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but introduce additional requirements related to application hosting services and end-to-end offerings including security (service availability, data sovereignty, workload isolation) often imposed by specific domain regulations [1]. On the other hand, MEC infrastructure needs to be integrated with target 5G infrastructure that is evolving to be more distributed and virtualized. Available resources in edge locations are usually limited, have finite extension capacity, and are more expensive than in a central Data Center. Therefore, beside proper design of edge Data Centers capacity, the optimization of resource usage becomes crucial for effective deployment of MEC.

In this paper, our focus is mainly on the problem of application placement, taking into account various constraints imposed by technical and business terms and conditions. We propose additional cybersecurity constraints that lead to isolation of workloads of different categories.

Our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We define a MEC infrastructure model that reflects a widespread vision for network operator edge computing service evolution and is described by parameters that impact the application placement;
- We propose a MEC application model, based on virtual machines, consistent with the infrastructure model, that can express the needs of application owners with respects to infrastructure resources;
- We explain the problem of application placement optimization with constraints including isolation constraints;
- We demonstrate the implementation of application orchestration, using the placement algorithm output, within an experimental environment.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II gives a literature review about MEC application placement. Section III presents a model of the MEC infrastructure within 5G network. Section IV describes our application placement problem. We discuss experimental implementation in Section V and conclude the paper in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Despite the growing interest in various forms of edge computing and 5G, there exist few works addressing the problem of the placement of MEC applications. The assumed models of applications, management frameworks and edge infrastructure are usually different in each work.

The application placement problem is often related to fog computing [2] or cloud computing [3]. Most of existing works consider edge computing as limited cloud computing resources located close to base stations. The distributed edge architecture is composed of 3 parts: devices connected to access network, edge servers, cloud data centers and the optimization objective is minimizing average response delay. In some works ETSI MEC is used as reference architecture and the placement algorithm is oriented toward availability of services offered by the MEC platform [4].

The constraints related to applications are associated with models of edge applications. Edge resources can be used for task offloading from mobile devices [5] [6] or heavily loaded application components from the cloud [7], providing network services [8] or serving different types of end-user applications [9]. Some works analyze specific edge computing use cases like Augmented Reality (AR) applications [10] [11]. MEC applications in the Network Function Virtualization (NFV) environment can form the mobile network service deployed as a Service Function Chain (SFC) leading to the SFC placement problem in a MEC-NFV environment [12].

The main discussed constraints determining the placement of workload on edge servers are the infrastructure parameters that have the impact on quality experienced by application users i.e. delays associated with computation and communication [13] [14], often taking into account the mobility of users and migration of applications [15] between edge locations. In order to improve the availability of edge-hosted applications, solutions based on affinity/anti-affinity rules [16], redundancy (backup VNFs [17]) or considering limited energy budget of servers to avoid failures [18] are proposed.

Sharing common computing resources by numerous independent customers leads to additional security constraints, often imposed by vertical industries' specific cybersecurity regulations. The "security by policy" approach, corresponding to our proposal, was used in [19]: to avoid privacy breaks or information leaks, a critical workload cannot be deployed on a computing element hosting other non-secure workloads.

Multiple works mentioned above are devoted to placement of virtual machines, but MEC can also be considered as a platform for hosting more lightweight workloads like Docker containers [21]. In the future, this solution may be more applicable to MEC due to their flexibility, including lightweight images and fast startup time.

III. PROPOSED MEC MODEL

We propose a model of MEC infrastructure and MEC applications that reflects the distributed nature of edge computing in 5G. Since the latency is a key driver for hosting applications at edge data centers, we can assume that multiple instances

of a given application are placed in the locations that allow serving end-devices within the required latency range.

For given geographical coordinates covered by 5G network, the route of the Data Plane packet from the device through radio, transport and Core networks to selected N6-LAN (i.e. the network of edge data center) can be specified and the respective latency - estimated. In this way, the available edge hosting infrastructure can be mapped to the area of 5G network coverage with latency estimation.

On the other hand, the Vertical or application provider, while designing the service, should estimate the number and location of devices accessing the application hosted in MEC. These estimations are the basis for specifying the needed number of instances of the application, together with computing resources (CPU, RAM) and preferred location of each instance.

Application instances deployed in MEC should fulfill the latency constraints. The other constraints - imposed by technical, business or legal conditions, should also be considered in the orchestration process. Therefore, we bring forward a more detailed model presented below.

A. MEC Architecture

The concept of edge computing in mobile network is standardized by ETSI around MEC RA (Reference Architecture) [20]. Meanwhile, 3GPP studies in edge computing in 5G networks brought specification of an architecture for enabling edge applications (EDGEAPP) in Rel-17 [22]. The relation between these architectures and potential synergies can be found in ETSI White Paper No. 36 [23]. The management and orchestration of MEC applications is mainly covered by ETSI standards, therefore we use processes and data models defined in ETSI standards as a basis for application placement in the orchestration phase.

B. Edge Infrastructure Model

The distributed nature of mobile network gives telecom operators the opportunity to build diversified edge computing infrastructure that can be used to create an "edge - cloud computing continuum". In order to ensure the network coverage and service quality, the operator builds geographically spread access network nodes connected by reliable and high-bandwidth transport network.

Taking into account the architecture of the transport network for 5G [24] and real estate assets of the operator, the edge computing infrastructure can be structured as follows:

- **Regional data centers** – providing new hosting capabilities for services based on NFV (Network Function Virtualization) - virtualization of legacy network functions and creation of new ones,
- **Local (also called Central Office) data centers** – offering additional hosting capabilities with low latency, reusing if possible the infrastructure developed for fixed network with placement usually correlated with density of population,

- **Cell Site data centers** for extreme edge use cases – located close to RAN (Radio Access Network) infrastructure - serving end-user devices in the area of one or multiple cells (denoted here as Service Area).

The edge infrastructure complements available central data centers, providing cloud services for the operator. As depicted in Fig.1, the edge computing infrastructure can be logically represented as a three-level hierarchical tree. Physical locations of devices can be mapped to the areas served by Cell Site data centers, the coverage of a set of Cell Site data center is aggregated in respective Local data center and finally the coverage of a set of Local data centers forms the area served by given Regional data center.

Fig. 1. Proposed Edge Infrastructure Model.

The quantity of possible Cell Site edge locations is much higher than Local or Regional data centers. Going up in the presented data center hierarchy increases transmission latency, but improves data center physical protection and available processing power. Going down the hierarchy brings higher costs (due to limited capacity of Cell Site edge data centers) but better QoS (Quality of Service) parameters. In general, the deployment of edge computing infrastructure can be spread over time and usually performed with a “top-down” approach, starting from a limited number of Regional data centers. In the following, we assume a fully-fledged edge computing continuum with 3 levels of data centers.

Table I presents the parameters we use to describe the edge computing infrastructure. Each data center location is identified by a reference (LOC_ID) which contains the indicators of its position in the infrastructure hierarchy (R_ID for regional data center, R_ID and CO_ID for local data center and R_ID, CO_ID, and SA_ID for Cell Site data center).

Every data center contains a set of servers devoted to hosting MEC applications, for the application placement optimization parameters of every server (ES_ID) need to be specified. These parameters include typical computing resource parameters (CPU, RAM, storage), virtualization related parameters (like overcommitting ratio for CPU or RAM), special server features (like number of available GPU or Hardware Security Module (HSM)) and operational parameters (Power consumption, CPU cost).

TABLE I
INFRASTRUCTURE PARAMETERS

Edge Infrastructure parameters	Description
R_ID	ID of Edge Region
CO_ID	ID of Central Office within R_ID
SA_ID	ID of Service Area within CO_ID
LOC_ID	For Edge Region: R_(R_ID) For Edge Central Office: CO_(R_ID, CO_ID) For Edge Service Area: SA_(R_ID, CO_ID, SA_ID)
ES(LOC_ID)	Array of edge server IDs in LOC_ID
ES_ID	ID of Edge Server
vCPU(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	vCPU capacity of ES_ID
Cost_vCPU(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	Cost of vCPU in ES_ID
Max_OCPU(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	Overcommitting of CPU capacity of ES_ID
RAM(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	RAM capacity of ES_ID
Max_ORAM(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	Overcommitting of RAM capacity of ES_ID
Storage(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	Storage capacity of ES_ID
GPU(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	GPU capacity of ES_ID
HSM(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	HSM capacity of ES_ID
P(LOC_ID, ES_ID)	Power consumption of ES_ID

C. Latency Analysis

Beside parameters included in Table I, the latency of data path from the device to the relevant MEC application is the crucial parameter for application placement. The latency depends on the location of the server hosting the application instance:

- server in regional data center: latency comes from RAN, transport access and aggregation network and internal data center network;
- server in local data center: latency comes from RAN, transport access network and internal data center network;
- server in Cell Site data center: latency comes from RAN and internal data center network.

The latency parameter should be calculated taking into consideration the location of devices served by application instance (mapped to one of areas served by Cell Site data center). For a given device location, the latency towards the data center running the application instance in the infrastructure tree, must be estimated. In the simplest approach, we use a fixed value of latency (based on measurements in the real infrastructure) for each level of the infrastructure hierarchy tree. More precise latency parameters may be calculated if the value of latency for each element of the infrastructure is known or estimated.

D. Edge Application Model

In order to achieve low latency and high resiliency of services based on MEC, applications should be deployed in multiple locations as virtual machines. We propose to define common parameters of applications and additional instance-specific parameters.

TABLE II
MEC APPLICATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Description
MEC Application Parameters	
MA_ID	ID of MEC application
L(MA_ID)	Latency between given MEC and served UEs
QoS(MA_ID)	QoS class of MEC application
MC(MA_ID)	Migration cost of MEC application instance
I(MA_ID)	Array of MEC application instances
MEC Application Instance Parameters	
I_ID(MA_ID)	ID of Instance of MEC application
LOC(MA_ID,I_ID)	Requested location of the instance placement.
vCPU(MA_ID,I_ID)	Required vCPU capacity of MEC application instance
vRAM(MA_ID,I_ID)	Required RAM capacity of MEC application instance
Storage(MA_ID,I_ID)	Required Storage capacity of MEC application instance
GPU(MA_ID,I_ID)	Required GPU for MEC application instance
HSM(MA_ID,I_ID)	Required HSM for MEC application instance

As presented in Table II, applications are described by required latency upper bound, parameters related to required quality of service, and willingness to migrate the application instance between data centers after deployment. For each application, the set of its instances needs to be described by providing its preferred geographical location (as a result of anticipated location of devices) and computing resource parameters (CPU, RAM, storage) as well as required special server features, such as GPU (Graphical Processing Unit) or HSM (Hardware Security Module).

IV. APPLICATION PLACEMENT PROBLEM

Having the infrastructure model and its associated MEC application model, we define the optimal application placement problem. Its purpose is to provide a placement for every specified application instance on one of the available servers from the edge infrastructure, while taking into account service and technical constraints.

A. Security constraints

The constraints currently defined are related to latency requirements and to the utilization of available resources. However, security requirements can also be a part of a Service Level Agreement (SLA) for hosting applications in MEC. As indicated in [25], the MEC system must be secured according to the best practices of server security, virtualization infrastructure security and address additional MEC specific threats. Inside a MEC data center, both isolation of resources and data must be guaranteed between MEC applications, since they may belong to different tenants, users, or network slices. However, the separation of physical resources dedicated to different MEC applications is not technically and economically feasible for all tenants due to limited resources and associated costs.

In addition to using various protection technologies like system hardening techniques, system-level authentication and access control, physical controls, communications security,

software integrity protection, TEE (Trusted execution environment), HSM (Hardware Security Module), physically isolating sensitive workloads from non-sensitive ones is recommended in multi-tenant virtualized environments. This way, sensitive workloads are not exposed to the impact of breaching the isolation within the non-sensitive group. Since physical isolation is not economically feasible, this approach can be applied in MEC application orchestration phase with additional constraints related to placement of application instances on shared resources.

Initially, for the isolation constraints, the following hypothesis is used: *MEC application instances can be placed on the same physical node if and only if each of them has security level equal or higher than the maximum of requested isolation levels by each of them.* It assumes that security level ($SLV(MA_ID)$) is determined for each MEC application and application owner may request isolation level $I_s(MA_ID)$ not higher than $SLV(MA_ID)$:

$$\forall_{MA_ID} \quad I_s(MA_ID) \leq SLV(MA_ID)$$

Security level of each MEC application needs to be determined in a security assessment process using criteria such as:

- VM image vulnerability scanning results;
- security of base OS image used for MEC application image;
- security of development process (programming language, libraries, open-source components, etc.);
- security of application testing.

On the other hand, isolation requirement for each application instance is defined by application owner using application security level and analysis of impact of MEC application on the security of the whole Vertical service. The resulting anti-affinity rules prevent placement of sensitive applications on the same resources as non-sensitive and potentially more vulnerable applications that can be taken over in order to perform attack on isolation.

The isolation constraints express the need for isolation for a given application: if the application is sensitive to isolation breach, it should require the highest possible isolation level that depends on the application's own security level.

B. Optimization criteria

In order to efficiently use available resources, the placement of MEC application instances should be optimal, and the following optimization criteria can be considered:

- **Latency** – the overall latency of all instances should be minimized: such a placement will offer the best quality (the lowest latency) for application users, but it will enforce use of servers located close to devices (which are typically the most expensive), however, for some applications, improvements of latency beyond the required level can go unnoticed;
- **Cost** – the cost of running all application instances (the cost of used vCPUs) should be minimized: it will give competitive advantage for application/service providers hosting their application in MEC;

- **Energy consumption** – the cost of energy for running all application instances should be minimized: it will prefer more energy efficient edge servers to support greener operations.

For real-life edge deployment, multi-criteria optimization combining the different criteria is the target solution.

C. Optimization algorithm

The optimal application placement can be found by modeling the problem as an ILP (Integer Linear Programming) formulation and then solving it to optimality.

We model the problem by defining a set of nodes corresponding to the hosts. We consider a set of instances associated to each application. Decision variables are binary ones and consists in deciding for each application and each node if an instance of the application has to be placed on the node (then the value is 1), or not (corresponding to the value 0).

The different constraints of the problem formulation are:

- capacity constraints: to make sure that nodes can support the placed application instances, in terms of CPU, RAM, and storage;
- latency constraints: to guarantee that applications could be reached within a latency value lower than a required threshold (corresponding to the SLA of the application);
- placement constraints: to ensure that each instance is placed exactly once;
- anti-affinity constraints: to make sure that different instances of the same application cannot be placed on the same node;
- and isolation constraints: so that the isolation level of an application is above (or equal to) the security level of all the other applications placed on the same node.

Due to space limitation, the complete formulation and implementation details are not given here.

The initial placement can be treated as an offline problem. Addition or termination of instances in online mode can be achieved by iterating the resolution of a similar model, taking into account instance migration cost and current instance location. Placement optimization results indicate a MEC server for each MEC application instance and can be used in the application orchestration process.

V. ORCHESTRATION WITH PLACEMENT OPTIMIZATION

A. Extension of MEC Orchestrator

The functions of MEC Orchestrator, defined by ETSI in [20], include:

- maintaining an overall view of the MEC system based on deployed MEC hosts, available resources, available MEC services, and topology;
- on-boarding of application packages (checking the integrity and authenticity of the packages, validating application rules and requirements, keeping a record of on-boarded packages, and preparing the infrastructure managers to handle the applications);

- selecting appropriate MEC hosts for application instantiation based on constraints, such as: latency, available resources, and available services;
- triggering application instantiation and termination;
- triggering application relocation as needed when supported.

We propose to include placement optimization in the “*application instantiation based on constraints*” function, by extending the set of constraints and specifying the physical server that the application instance should be deployed on.

Fig. 2. Orchestration with placement optimization.

As depicted in Fig.2, the MEC Orchestrator receives the necessary information in *App Manifest* and *App Deployment* files together with the application image. These files extend data models and data formats defined by ETSI for application package, application descriptor, application instance [26] with the necessary parameters for placement with constraints (e.g. security and isolation levels, proposed instance locations, etc.).

B. The role of placement algorithm

The initial orchestration process consists of the following steps (cf. Fig. 2):

- 1) Application providers deliver MEC application images together with data in *App Manifest* and *App Deployment* files.
- 2) MEC Orchestrator collects all MEC applications data and sends request to Placement module to calculate the optimal placement for all application instances in the given infrastructure topology.
- 3) Based on placement optimization results, MEC Orchestrator sends appropriate MEC application instances data to respective MEC Infrastructure Manager.
- 4) MEC Infrastructure Manager instantiates requested MEC application instances on specified servers of Edge infrastructure.

C. Implementation and Setup

The proposed process of application orchestration using the results of the placement optimization algorithm was implemented using Python language within our MEC experimental environment based on OpenStack [27].

The MEC Orchestrator module gathers and presents information about the MEC infrastructure and MEC applications

using the Graphical User Interface. Then it converts the data into internal format and communicates with the Placement algorithm. After receiving placement results, it requests launching all applications instances on indicated servers.

The Placement module receives the data on the topology, MEC applications and instances and uses the CBC solver [28] to find the optimal instances' placement. The MEC Infrastructure Manager receives information about instances from MEC Orchestrator and provides information about managed infrastructure and running applications. It runs/terminates the application on the infrastructure using the Terraform tool.

VI. SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS

In this paper, we proposed a model for the MEC infrastructure and MEC applications, and defined the problem of optimal application placement taking into account various constraints including isolation of workloads. These models were integrated with the optimal application placement problem, formulated with Integer Linear Programming. Finally, the experiment with the proposed data models and placement optimization algorithm for MEC applications orchestration on the OpenStack platform, was set up and presented.

The physical isolation based only on the security level of other applications sharing the same resources is the initial approach to define security constraints. Other solutions can cover hardware anchoring, hardened virtualization, isolation monitoring, ...; but in every case, the isolation constraints impact the placement of application on available resources.

The next steps will include the evaluation of the proposed placement optimization algorithm for different input data and the comparison of results with results achieved with simple greedy algorithms. Another interesting direction to investigate is the orchestration of containerized workloads. We will study how the proposed models should be modified to cover growing in popularity Cloud Native technologies.

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